

THE ROLE OF FAIRY TALES IN UPBRINGING CHILDREN

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At the present time effective upbringing and education in our country is praised and it is aimed at forming a comprehensively advanced generation, and it has reached the level of state policy in our country.

Tale stories in bringing up a healthy and comprehensively advanced generation, as well as bringing up talented young people who are appropriate for the requirements of the 21st century is particularly important. Therefore, teaching pupils at a high quality, bring up them in the spirit of loyalty and respect for the motherland, and also for universal values.

Process of telling tales should include educational purposes such as respect for the wisdom and values of the wise, hygiene, liberty, dress code, children's rights, nature conservation, greetings and behavior, love for books, to form and strengthen moral values in children.

It is important to invite them to learn more fairy tales, to educate their moral qualities through fairy tales, and to encourage them to read more books. Influencing children's emotional world – is considered to be a vital task.

The aims of fairy tales are considered to grow children as a modest man and a humanist, also to teach them to value the good, to respect adults as a sample of tale characters. For this reason, we should enrich the pupil of preschools, the life and activities of schoolboys with meaningful fairy tales. Organizing creative, moral, social, and social behavioral experience should be the main factor in the development of their childhood.

Educating the students with fairy-tale is carried out under the supervision of the educator. This should be accompanied by a combination of the system of knowledge – the natural, ethical and ideological knowledge system.

Psychologists L.I Bojovich and his staff emphasized that the school children's life not only should be organized accurately, improve the experience of correct behavior but also should be up-brought appropriately the motives of system of emotions.

Therefore, the true behavior experience can reach certain aim if this behavior is based on specific motives. It is therefore important to train and strengthen the motivational motives of behavior with fairy tales. Schoolchildren should be encouraged to gain positive experiences in fairytales through educational experiences in certain situations from the very beginning.

'Fairy tales are considered the most important way to build a moral mind is to enrich and summarize the ethical experience by creating the right behavior among the learners. Through various forms of morality in reading, through fairy tales we can observe their perceptions and feelings through lively, brilliant words and discussions.

Additionally, fairytales inspire the children improve their positive feelings and qualities and refuse their negative behavior. What's more, they object to help children be in critical attitude to themselves, understand carefully qualities of their behavior, and see clearly the defects of their own. Through fairy tales mentors help children

- to organize the program of upbringing themselves
- to develop the children's positive emotions – self-confidence, persistence
- to strive to get rid of the bad one – laziness, stubbornness and rudeness of their own conduct.

Finally, by fairy-tales the teacher or the educator presents wisest ways of self-education. They show the best and most effective ways to build a positive image of the family and to eliminate shortcomings.

The discipline is aimed at forming mind of a child, and it involves the process of building a life of beliefs and emotions and spiritualities. 'Promoting education and upbringing to create the demands of the modern life ...' [1:73]

'National Program for Personnel Training' means that among other important issues, it is necessary to raise the moral and ethical attitudes of the students on the basis of the ideology of revival and the wealth of the society, the formation of the culture of behavior of the pupils, and the formation of a genuine person by the comprehension of a harmonious generation.

The goals and objectives of the present day are primarily to educate the young people as a genuine person, to appreciate human dignity, our national values, to live in freedom and in a free society, to be a selfless human being, worthy of our independent state in the international community.

As children treat fairy tales, positive and negative attitudes can emerge. Positive attitude to the fairy tale, interest in science, diligence, and negative attitude can lead to empathy, laziness, and lack of self-control. Therefore, it is advisable to consider fairy tales as a means of influencing the formation of their role in the lives of children [2. P.69].

It is important to use universal and national values to educate the moral qualities of young people through fairy tales. Universal and national values and their role in shaping children are important. The revival of our national traditions and tales will be the basis for establishing the moral norms based on national and universal values, and bringing them up to the minds of our children to educate them as a selfless, knowledgeable person for our society.

National tales are the product of spiritual life of every nation, and the public opinion of that nation turns national traditions into their spiritual need. National tales bring up social consciousness in young people and play an important role in the formation of their full-fledged personality. It actively participates in the formation of a child's character and psychologically affects youth ideology.

Spiritual consciousness and integrity are important in shaping the spiritual qualities of the child through the tales. Young talents are self-conscious, self-imposed, feeling the difference between good and bad, fair and unfair and these in self-discipline form psychological mechanisms of education [3. P.91].

Self-discipline includes four tasks:

1. The desire to develop the child's positive qualities and to abstain from his negative behavior.
2. Help the child to be critical of his or her personality, to be attentive and reasonable to his attitudes, to help him or her to see his or her faults, and to help understand his or her shortcomings.
3. Identify the characteristics of child traits that need to be developed and eliminated in the development of self-education plan.
4. Teachers should identify reasonable ways of educating a learner.

Educating children in the spirit of patriotism and formation of patriotism through the tales:

1. Teaching children to love motherland and respect for native country.

2. Introducing the essence of the independent Uzbekistan concept to the students' minds.
3. Teaching young people to respect the national traditions, customs, language, culture and mentality of our people.
4. Saving the spiritual values left by our great ancestor's, understanding the importance of history for today.
5. Inspiring belief, healthy thinking and power of in youth.
6. Understanding responsibility for the Motherland and the essence of the struggle for the benefit of the nation.
7. Organizing the experience for students to respect their native country, their parents, and their teacher.

It is well known that on 'Law on Education and the National Program for Personnel Training' child development is accepted as a main issue. In our country, necessary work is being done to implement these tasks. The radical change in the content of educational work in school has become one of the prior issues of today [4.85].

Particularly, fairy tales involve both upbringing and educational aspects. Taking into account the psychological features of each age period, interaction through fairy tales creates self-esteem in children. The sooner the child feels the sense of self-consciousness, the sooner he develops his mental and physical abilities, his perception of his or her own rights. At the same time, there is a psychological barrier to the content of whims, stubbornness, and persistence.

In general, the use of family, educational institutions and fairy tales in all aspects of social life is a prerequisite for studying the positive relationship between education and upbringing and increasing productivity.

In the past, our ancestors have not studied the psychological laws of human beings, even though they have not been studied in a specific scientific direction, but the manifestations of these states in the manuscripts of the scholars and their wise ideas about human perfection are of high importance [5. p.118].

One of the main issues of Yusuf Hos Hojib's work is to bring up a perfect man. He describes the perfect man, in his writings, and he has his principles, as he imagined a man who could meet the requirements of society at that time. His work 'Qutadg'ubilig' – 'The Giver of Knowledge' – 'Saodatga eltuvchi yo'l' is spiritual sources of morality combine the teaching and instructional ways, spiritual instruction and methods. Abdurahmon Jamiy's expressed his thoughts on science, education, vocational training and positive human qualities in the works of 'Bahoriston', 'Hirandnomai Iskandari', 'Tuxfatul Akhrar' and others [6. P.94].

The poetry of Alisher Navoi 'Khazoyin ulmaoniy', 'Mahbubul Qulub' and many others have made valuable comments on the ethics, spirituality, attitudes, talents and abilities of a mature, competent person. It emphasizes that these criteria are crucial for the solution of social justice. Also, in Navoi's works, the role of the parents, the people's humility in the formation of the younger generation as a complementary person occupy a special place.

Each episode of Navoi's 'Hamsa' is characterized by its indefinable willpower, determination, obedience, human emotion, creative imagination, and intricate internal experiences of man. in this regard, the views of the great Oriental thinkers such as Mahmud Koshghari, Ulugbek, Nakshbandi, Ogahi, in the stories of fairy tales, morals, courtesy, family life, interpersonal relationships, can be emphasized [7. P.64].

As we know, the fairy-tales are the genre of oral folklore. The fairytales in oral folklore are the leading places. The wisdom of the common people, a few generations, is the result of the wisdom and wisdom of life. The summary of a life story that describes the taste of life, the mind-looking, pure conscience, the noble, the wise, the hardworking person, the event, any person, or any other work. This conclusion serves as a guide for children in life. The stories are created as the folklore, folklore, historical experience, struggle and artistic expression of labor.

It will be an important tool for children to become perfect people who will live for the future of our Homeland. Thus, the fairy tale is a rich, unique and impressive genre. Another important feature of fairy tale is that it encourages children from their early age to love nature and preserve the animals. They are deeply conscious of the need for feeding dogs, cats, all pets and even mice [8. P.73].

Through the fairy tales we can achieve:

- formation and development of their outlook;
- increasing their love for nature;
- moral and spiritual education;
- giving concept about goodness always win over evil;
- interest in science;

This is the best way to make the readers aware, intelligent, true, and patriotic.

The pictures in the fairy tales also serve to educate the students in the light of the above requirements. Using the pictures of fairy tales to create and develop concepts about motherland, to increase love and loyalty to Homeland, to appreciate the beautiful nature of our Motherland, natural wealth, to achieve such qualities as love, kindness, friendship, harmony, and knowledge. Below are some of the pictures of the pedagogical value of the pictures.

The pictures on the fairy tale make it easier for children to be patriotic, straightforward and kind. They are the means to educate their readers as patriots who love the country and are the ones who are spiritually mature, who are caring for the Motherland. The ability to apply these pictures to the students depends on the teacher's skill.

Upbringing of pupils on the basis of the ideals of national independence is in the process of the education of the present day. The main requirement of the educational reform is that the pupils are fully competent, spiritually-educational and meet international educational standards and upbringing.

At the same time, the students need to have the basic idea of national ideology of independence – the development of the Motherland, the peace of the country in the minds of the readers.

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